

Table 2. Effect of LFA and added P on grain and straw yields of IR20 in lateritic sandy clay loam soil. 1988.

Treatment LFA (g/pot)	Yield			
	Grain (g/pot)	% increase	Straw (g/pot)	% increase
		<i>P</i> (0 ppm)		
No added LFA	16.29		20.47	
2.5	17.48	7.3	22.68	10.8
5.0	23.07	41.6	27.72	35.4
7.5	16.81	3.2	17.64	-13.8
Mean	18.81		22.12	
		<i>P</i> (13 ppm)		
No added LFA	17.25		25.08	
2.5	19.31	11.9	24.23	-3.4
5.0	23.62	36.9	33.40	33.2
7.5	16.07	-6.8	17.18	-31.5
Mean	19.06		24.97	
LSD (<i>P</i> = 0.05)				

diammonium phosphate at 13 ppm, and K as sulfate potash at 11 ppm.

Twenty-day-old rice seedlings raised in the experimental soil were transplanted at two seedlings per hill, three hills per

pot, and allowed to grow for 50 d under flooded condition.

LFA combined with NPK resulted in the highest DMP (22.7 g/pot), which was about 42% more than that of NPK alone

(Table 1). P content was consistently higher when LFA was added. LFA with N, P, K, and their combinations did not influence SiO₂ content in rice plants.

Another pot culture trial in Dec 1987-Apr 1988 incorporated 0, 2.5, 5.0, and 7.5 g LFA/pot (0, 0.5, 1.0, and 1.5 t/ha) with 13 ppm P and no P. The experiment was conducted using a completely randomized design with three replications. N at 40 ppm and K at 11 ppm were applied to all pots.

Regardless of P treatment, LFA at 5 g/pot gave the highest grain yield, followed by LFA at 2.5 g/pot (Table 2). Applying P with LFA at 2.5 g/pot increased grain yield, but at 7.5 g LFA/pot, yields were reduced by 6.8% compared with no LFA.

Straw yield was markedly increased with 5 g LFA/pot with or without P. LFA at 7.5 g/pot adversely affected straw yield.

Silicicolous plants, such as rice, can benefit from up to 1 t LFA/ha, particularly in lateritic acid soils. ■

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Using desiccation to preserve blue-green algae (BGA)

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We wanted to find a suitable method to preserve BGA in the dry state as an alternative to frequent subculturing of fresh cultures. We produced soil-based cultures, cultures deposited on paper strips, and mass cultures and tested their viabilities after long storage.

Soil-based cultures were produced in 250-ml erlenmeyer flasks or on petri plates (14 cm diam). A loopful of culture was inoculated into a previously autoclaved mixture of 100 ml BG-11₀ medium and 20 g soil. Cultures were incubated under continuous illumination for 4 wk and then dried slowly. Cultures were ground and kept in plastic bottles at room temperature.

To preserve strains on paper, 6- to 12-wk-old liquid cultures were deposited aseptically on to sterile strips (2 × 7.8 cm)

of Whatman chromatography paper no. 3 and dried in a convection flow clean bench. Paper strips were stored in plastic bags at room temperature.

Mass cultures were produced in 12 liters of medium exposed to continuous illumination, stirring, and bubbling of an air-CO₂ mixture. Cultures were decanted and centrifuged after 4-6 wk of growth. They were dried slowly under fluorescent lamps and later ground and stored in plastic bottles.

Viabilities of the dried cultures were tested by incubating aliquot parts of the soil-based and mass cultures in 25-ml erlenmeyer flasks containing 5 ml of medium. For cultures on paper strips, 0.5-cm portions were cut and incubated like the other cultures.

Of the 65 soil-based cultures, 58 remained viable after 6 yr of storage. A disadvantage of using soil as a base is the presence of contaminants. About 40% of the cultures were contaminated with either diatoms, BGA (notably *Nostoc* sp.), or both. Soil must be sterilized completely to remove indigenous flora when using this preservation method.

Fifteen of the 136 strains dried on paper strips lost viability after at least 5 mo of storage. The number increased to 30 after another 6 mo, and none of the strains were viable after 4 yr. The paper strip method should only be used for short-term preservation.

Powdered mass cultures remained viable after 9 yr of storage. As with the soil-based cultures, the populations decreased tremendously over time; higher aliquot parts and longer incubation periods were required to obtain growth. The best method for preserving BGA in the dry state is the powdered mass culture, which has the advantages of unialgality and retention of viability for up to 9 yr. ■

Effects of *Sesbania aculeata* (dhaincha) on rice yield

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We studied how rice yields were affected by green manuring with dhaincha and by incorporating green manure (GM) with graded doses of N, P, K, and Zn (see table).

Effect of graded doses of NPK with and without dhaincha on rice yield, yield attributes, and profit.^a Hisar, India.

	12.5 t dhaincha/ha + 120 N + 13.2 P + 24.9 K + 5.75 Zn ^b kg/ha	180 N + 13.2 P + 24.9 K + 5.75 Zn kg/ha	125 N + 27.28 P + 51.46 K + 5.75 Zn kg/ha	LSD 0.05
Rice yield (t/ha)	8.7	8.2	7.4	0.4
Increase in yield (t/ha) over 125 kg N/ha treatment	1.3	0.8	-	
Increase in yield (t/ha) over 180 kg N/ha treatment	0.4	-	-	
Expenditure on fertilizer, including dhaincha (US\$/ha)	65.30	51.70	50.85	
Yield price (US\$/ha)	880.57	836.79	753.32	
Net profit (US\$/ha)	522.32	492.14	409.52	
Increase in profit (US\$/ha) over 125 kg N/ha treatment	112.80	82.62	-	
Increase in profit (US\$/ha) over 180 kg N/ha treatment	30.18	-	-	
Benefit-cost ratio over 125 kg N/ha treatment	8.8:1			
180 kg N/ha treatment	3.2:1			
Yield attributes				
Plant height (cm)	85.6	88.5	85.7	0.79
1,000-grain wt (g)	26.0	25.9	25.0	ns ^c
Tillers (no.)	18.0	17.6	16.9	ns
Soil data (postharvest)				
pH (1:2)	8.2	8.4	8.3	ns
EC (1:2)	0.12	0.14	0.16	
OC (%)	0.24	0.23	0.22	
Available P (kg/ha)	7.20	8.00	8.80	
Available K (kg/ha)	250	253	268	

^aPrice (US\$/kg): N = 0.19, P = 0.22, K = 0.08, Zn = 0.34, rice = 0.10. Expenditure on all agricultural operations = US\$292.95/ha. ^bZn = zinc sulfate. ^cns = not significant.

Soil of the experimental field was classified as sandy loam (Typic Ustochrept) with pH 8.3, 0.30% organic C, EC (1:2) 0.15 dS/m, CEC 10.5 meq/100 g soil, 150 kg available N/ha (alkaline permanganate method), 9.0 kg available P/ha (NaHCO₃ extract), and 260 kg available K/ha (ammonium acetate extract). Available Zn was 0.58 ppm (DTPA extractable).

Dhaincha sown in another field was cut at 45 d, transported, and incorporated into the soil at 12.5 t/ha. N was 1.1% of fresh biomass. Rice variety HKR-120 (145 d) was planted in the field.

One-third of the N as urea and full doses of P, K, and Zn were applied at transplanting. The remaining N was applied in two equal splits at 3 and 6 wk after transplanting. The experiment was laid out in randomized block design with three replications. The experimental plot was 0.3 ha.

GM and 120 kg N/ha yielded significantly more than 125 kg N/ha and about the same as 180 kg N/ha. This resulted in a net profit of US\$30/ha (see table). ■

Crop management

Comparative yields and N uptake in six transplanted and direct seeded lowland rices

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We compared yields and N uptake of six rice varieties in a submerged Entisol under transplanted and direct seeded cultures. The field experiment was conducted on Manmool clay soil (deep aquic Ustorthent) with pH 6.6 and 0.13% total N at the Ramachandrapuram farm of DRR during the 1990 wet season (WS).

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design, with direct seeded rice and transplanted rice in the main plots. Subplot treatments were the six varieties. Rice was direct seeded at 100 kg seed/ha. Pregerminated seeds were broadcast in half of the main field and in nursery beds on 10 Jul. No standing water was allowed in the direct seeded plots for 2 wk during seedling establishment. Water level was kept at 5-7 cm during the growing season.

Three-week-old seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing in the remaining half of the main field on 3 Aug. Eighty kg N, 17 kg P, and 33 kg K/ha were uniformly applied. All of the P and K were applied to the field 1 d before seeding or transplanting. N was applied in three splits for the direct seeded crop: 25% at seeding, 25% at 3 wk after seeding, and 50% at panicle initiation (PI). N was applied in two equal splits at planting and at PI in the transplanted crops. Grain and straw were sampled at maturity to determine total N uptake.

Grain and straw yields did not vary significantly with crop establishment method. Sasyashree produced significantly higher straw and lower grain yields than did the other varieties. Culture type and variety had significant interaction effect on straw yields but not grain yields. Rasi and IET9219 produced more straw under direct seeding than